

Guidelines for Adjudicating Hand-Coded Data

Higher Ed Protest Event Dataset (HiPED) Project

Authors: Alex Hanna and Ellen Berrey

alex.hanna@gmail.com, ellen.berrey@utoronto.ca

Last updated: June 22, 2026

NOTE TO EXTERNAL READERS.....	3
INTRODUCTION.....	3
Prerequisites.....	3
Purpose of Adjudication.....	3
How to Use this Document.....	4
Terminology.....	4
I. ADJUDICATION WORKFLOW.....	4
Step 1: Check your Assigned Start-Date Range/Location.....	6
Step 2: Enter Filters/Sort Criteria and Pull Assigned Search List.....	6
Step 3: Review Candidate Events List.....	6
Step 4: Create a New Canonical Event Record and Key (if relevant).....	7
Step 5: Referee Candidate Events and Add Information to Canonical Event Record.....	8
Step 6: Select New Candidate Events (if relevant).....	9
Step 7: Add Relationships.....	9
Step 8: Record Your Progress in the Adjudicator Assignments Spreadsheet.....	14
II. REFEREEING: STEP 5 IN DETAIL.....	14
Basics of Refereeing.....	15
Working with Text Selects: Matching with Presets and Other Considerations.....	18
Adjudicating Police Actions.....	20
Friendly Reminders: Known Errors in Prior Coding that Can Be Easily Corrected.....	22
Refereeing Complications.....	22
III. ADDING INFORMATION USING ADJUDICATOR-CREATED VARIABLES.....	23
IV. RETURNING TO THE PASS 1 MPEDS INTERFACE TO CODE.....	24
A. To Correct or Add Important Information Missing from an Existing Candidate Event Record or Correct Existing Information Related to Where the Protest Occurred.....	24
B. To Create a New Candidate Event.....	25

V. AD HOC ADJUDICATION.....	26
Montreal 2012 and Montreal 2015.....	26
VI. QUALITY CONTROL/FEEDBACK.....	27
Feedback Partners.....	27
APPENDICES.....	29
Glossary.....	29
Interface Screenshots.....	31

NOTE TO EXTERNAL READERS

We continually updated the *Adjudication Guidelines* with clarifications, further instructions, and decisions on particular events throughout the coding process. This version of the *Adjudication Guidelines* has been modified slightly to include explanatory notes and formatting changes; however, the content is the same as the original document which research assistants referred to as they coded adjudicated event codings.

All footnotes are explanatory for external readers. Hyperlinks to internal project documents were removed, but noted.

INTRODUCTION

Prerequisites

This document provides instructions for adjudicating hand-coding of protest events, for RAs previously trained on the higher-education protest project codebook. It is expected that you already understand the codebook and have experience using it to code protest events before using the adjudication guidelines.

Purpose of Adjudication

Adjudicating the human codings of protest events serves three main purposes:

1. Create one authoritative and complete “canonical event” record for each unique protest event. To achieve this, you may need to:
 - *Referee between multiple codings of the same article*
 - *Referee between codings of the same protest event reported in different articles*
 - *Correct errors and perform minor data cleaning*

2. Systematically label the relationships between canonical protest events.
3. Record article mentions for each canonical protest event.

Adjudicators are NOT expected to:

- Code new events from scratch.
- Re-read each article to correct previous coding (unless necessary, as described below)

Simply put, adjudicators will review and compare multiple event codings at the same time to determine which elements should become part of the new, compiled Canonical Event record for each unique protest event.

How to Use this Document

This document provides specific, functional instructions on the adjudication process and you will not need to reference it as frequently as the project codebook. You may still need to use the codebook to make decisions about relevant coding information.

Terminology

We have developed many new terms to clarify the adjudication process. Consult the [glossary](#) if you are confused about any new terms you come across in these guidelines.

I. ADJUDICATION WORKFLOW

Overview of the Process

When adjudicating, you will be creating a new canonical event record and/or adding information to an existing canonical event. Typically, you will first use a set of search tools within the adjudication interface to identify candidate event codings that potentially refer to the same canonical event. Then, using the expanded event view pane, you will referee the candidate events to identify relevant information and add that information to the canonical event.

If you are reading these guidelines for the first time, it may be helpful to open the adjudication interface to follow along with.

Figure 1. Visualization of Adjudication Process and Decision-Making

We anticipate that there will be three common scenarios adjudicators will encounter when considering candidate events:

1. A single canonical event is described in one candidate event coding, i.e. a singleton. In other words, the candidate event will become the canonical event.
2. A single canonical event is described in:
 - multiple candidate event codings of the same multiple-coded article and/or
 - multiple candidate event codings from different articles.

This will require you to sift through the candidate event codings to identify the most accurate information and any new information.

3. Multiple complex/related canonical events are described in multiple candidate codings of multiple articles. *These messier situations will require you to sift through the candidate events to identify the most accurate information and any new information, with an eye toward identifying relationships.*

In-Depth Workflow Instructions:

Step 1: Check your Assigned Start-Date Range/Location

Your first step should always be to check [your adjudicator assignments spreadsheet in Notion¹](#) to determine which start-date/location range you should be working on or to check where you have left off during your previous adjudication session.

Step 2: Enter Filters/Sort Criteria and Pull Assigned Search List

Using your adjudicator assignment, enter the correct search criteria in the “Search” tab ([screenshot](#)) of the event selection pane.

Filters: the criteria for candidate events to show up in your search results. We will primarily use start-date and location.

Sort: the order candidate events appear in your search. We will typically sort in this order: start date by chronological order, then form, and then article ID. If many protests are happening across universities in the same city in a narrow date range, publication name and/or University Name may also be included.

If a certain search generates an unmanageable number of candidate codings, you may need to refine the search, e.g. narrow the date range, include publication name. However, data managers will assign your searches so that further refinement will not likely be necessary.

The interface will store your most recent search terms so that you can easily access them while adjudicating, if relevant.

Step 3: Review Candidate Events List

Click on the “Candidate Events” tab ([screenshot](#)) to see the results of your search. You will need to review the candidate events to discern how many canonical events the search list contains. There are two categorizations to make mental note of:

¹ Internal document. We used the app “Notion” to create a custom spreadsheet view that broke down each adjudicator’s assignments. Adjudicators were assigned one year ranges for a specific city, starting with 2015-2018, then 2012-2014 since adjudicating events at the University of Missouri in fall 2015 were a priority for the project. We originally tested splitting up assigned candidate events by issue/racial-issue, but quickly abandoned that strategy since it did not allow adjudicators to catch duplicates with miscategorized issues (i.e. an event coded with a general issue that should have been racial).

1. What are the canonical event(s)? Focus on start-date, location, and form.

This is your main conceptual task. It may be helpful to make notes for yourself on paper, as you parse through the candidate events.

2. Do any candidate events come from articles that were multiple-coded? Look at article ID.

If so, you will need to manage duplicate and/or contradictory codings.

Typically, if you have sorted your assigned search correctly in the preceding step, then these mental categorizations should come fairly quickly, and should be revealed in the order of the candidate events list. You may wish to keep a piece of paper nearby so that you can jot down what you notice.

Once you have a clear (enough) picture of the candidate events and which canonical events they refer to, you will then start refereeing between the candidate event codings. Click “Add to Expand +” for any candidate events you wish to referee; you can view a max of four at the same time in the expanded view. The vast majority of the time, you should **start by refereeing the multiple codings**, before refereeing candidate events from different articles (see Figure 1 for clarity on the process). You will return to this step once you have refereed the multiple codings, so that you can then referee between the rest of the candidate events in your assigned search.

Step 4: Create a New Canonical Event Record and Key (if relevant)

If there is not a canonical event record for your selected candidate events, create a new canonical event record and assign it a key. In the expanded event, select “New Canonical Event” to create a new record. Within the pop-up window, assign the record a key using this exact format:

StartDate_Location(City)_Form_Issue

20170120_Atlanta_March_Trump(Against)

20140202_Toronto_SitIn_Labour

20140202_Toronto_SitIn-Contiguous_Labour

If there are multiple forms/issues for a canonical event, you may need to decide which one to use for the key. Use the most prominent issue/form based on the event description, using the exact preset language (Note: for presets with backslashes, select the most appropriate word even if it isn't the first, e.g. disruption). The keys are meant to be searchable by other adjudicators, not an exact representation of the event. Do not spend much time on this decision.

Duplicate Key Names

The adjudication interface will give you an error message if you enter a canonical key that already exists. If there are multiple canonical events with the same date/location/form/issue (which may be

the case for coinciding protests in large cities) then you can add the school after the location, or some other piece of differentiating information, using a hyphen:

Ex. 20160205_LosAngeles-UCLA_Strike_Labour

Since you are already in the expanded event view for this step, you can begin refereeing between your candidate events.

Step 5: Referee Candidate Events and Add Information to Canonical Event Record

This is the most important step in the workflow. You will be “refereeing” the existing candidate event codings to construct a single, authoritative record.

Now that you have selected candidate events and the corresponding canonical event record, you can hide the Event Selection pane by pressing “Hide Pane.” You should now have a full-screen view of all your candidate events side by side and your canonical event shaded in blue on the right.

Refer to [Part II](#) below for detailed instructions.

Within the candidate event grid, you may now begin adding new information to the canonical event record. If you are working with an existing canonical event record, **first, review that canonical event record fully**, so that you know what information already exists.

Second, for each candidate event, **confirm that the coding does in fact describe the canonical event**. If so, select the **link to canonical event** (details below).

Third, check every field for accuracy and completeness. If you are working with a singleton, this will be simpler because you will not need to compare and reconcile the singleton coding with other candidate events. If you are working with multiple candidate events, **go field by field across the candidate events** to referee the content, e.g., read through all the start dates, then all the end dates.

- Use the add button within each box to move that information into the canonical event record. If multiple candidate events include the exact same information, only rely on one of them to build the canonical event record.
- If you find inaccurate, insufficient, or incomplete information in the canonical event record, remove it with the “x” button and replace it with new information from one of your candidate events.
- As of 2022/01/27: Do NOT add any University Responses or Police Actions text-select from regular coder accounts into canonical event records.

Fourth, update the appropriate event actions...

Candidate Event Actions (Refer to [interface screenshot](#))

Link to canonical event to record an event mention: Press the “Link to canonical event” button for every candidate event that describes the canonical event you’re working on, whether or not it adds information to the canonical event record. When linked to a loaded canonical event record, the button turns red. Note that every candidate event should be linked to a canonical event (unless the original coder made an error and should never have been coded it in the first place). Any individual candidate event can be linked to multiple canonical event records.

Note: “Linking” an event mention links the Article ID to the canonical record; therefore, you will see the link button automatically turn red for other candidate events in your grid from the same article while that canonical event is open.

Note: Candidate events that are used to build a canonical event record are automatically linked to that record, even though that’s not visible through the adjudication interface.

Flag for later: the candidate event requires further review, and an issue has been reported in the [adjudication questions/issues spreadsheet in Notion](#).²

Mark completed: the candidate event coding has been refereed and does not to be consulted again. You will also use this button to “reject” candidate events that should have been disqualified. Pressing this button will also remove the candidate event from your grid.

Remove from grid: simply removes the selected candidate event from your grid. It will remain visible in your candidate events search results.

Disqualifying Candidate Events

If you notice that a candidate event should have been disqualified (i.e. it does not meet the essential criteria from the Pass 1 Codebook), simply add it to your grid, confirm that it should have been disqualified, and then “mark completed.”

Step 6: Select New Candidate Events (if relevant)

Remove the candidate events from the expanded view by marking them as complete. Before removing your chosen canonical event from the expanded view, you should return to the event selection pane (by pressing “Show Events”), to confirm that no more candidate events correspond to that canonical event. If there are more candidate events, start again from [Step 3](#) (Review Candidate Events List). If not, update the relationships tab (if relevant) before removing your candidate event.

² Internal document. We used the app “Notion” to create a custom spreadsheet to track adjudicator questions for follow-up during our intermittent team meetings.

Step 7: Add Relationships

In this step, you will take standardized notes on how the canonical event you are working on is related to other canonical events. Those other events may or may not also be in your assigned search.

Note (as of 2022-03-11): The interface feature is complete so we are no longer doing note on all relationships notes. All relationships should be captured using the codes within the Relationships tab of the event selection pane.³

Descriptions of Possible Relationships

If relevant, you will be adding information on one or more of these **four** possible relationships to a canonical event. For every relationship, there is at least one “child” canonical event and one “parent” canonical event.

- **Counterprotest:** a protest in opposition to the original protest and/or action or a reactionary protest aiming to show a different position than another protest.
 - The counterprotest is the child. The base protest that it is reacting against is the parent. You don't need to create an umbrella event.
 - If two protests are occurring on the same date and same location on opposing issues, but it is not entirely clear which is the protest and which is the counterprotest, use these guidelines:
 - If a group is protesting against a speaker or other event (happening or canceled), this is the protest. If a group is protesting for the speaker or other event (happening or canceled), this is the counterprotest. *The rationale is that, for our analyses, what is most important is identification of the protest/counter-protest dyad and consistency. In these cases, it is likely that the counter-protest would not have happened if not for the protest, although the dynamics are complex.*
- **Solidarity:** Double-check the Event Description and/or “Text Select: Related protests involving other universities” for any language suggesting it was a solidarity protest, even if it uses other related language, such as: “students wanted to demonstrate their unity with students protesting at X university;” “students were taking inspiration from...;” “protestors said they were standing with/showing support for the union strike.”
 - The solidarity event is the child. The inspiration protest is the parent. Note that the inspiration protest may be an umbrella event (most likely, for a campaign), e.g., when a protest is showing solidarity with Mizzou but not a specific Mizzou protest.

³ The “Relationships Tab” in the MPEDS adjudication interface was not finished when we started the adjudication process. Originally, the guidelines contained instructions on creating notes with standardized wording within the canonical event records’ “notes” field. After completing one academic year’s worth of candidate event codings the relationships tab was complete, and we created relationships directly in the interface and removed those notes from the records.

- **Campaign:** A series of events that are typically within the same university, but might be across universities. Events are explicitly coordinated. These could occur over a very short time period (even 1-2 days) or a much longer one, such as many months. Eg. System-wide labour strike, or the main Mizzou events.
 - Each canonical event in the campaign will be a child. The umbrella event for the campaign will be the parent.
 - You do not need to link child events from the same campaign together. They should link them all independently to the same parent umbrella event.
- **Coinciding:** Series of events typically across multiple universities/municipalities on the same date(s) or within a specific time frame, but the events are not explicitly coordinated. Eg. a National Day of Action, Million Student March.⁴
 - Each coinciding canonical event will be a child. The umbrella event for the coinciding events will be the parent.

If you make any observations about relationships between protest events which aren't captured with the standardized descriptions, flag the candidate events for review and submit a question to the Notion spreadsheet. If the canonical event is a single protest event in one location with no apparent connection to any other protest, it will have no relationships to record.

“Breakaway” protests: If you encounter a situation where a small subset of protesters from one event “breakaway” and start a new event that is distinct from the original, please adjudicate them as separate events but make a note of this dynamic in the Notes sections for the second event; please write “BREAKAWAY from [Canonical Event Key]”. You do not need to add any relationships.

Adding a Relationships

1. Open the event selection pane and then the “Relationships” tab.
2. In the first box, enter the canonical event key for the child event.
3. Select which relationship is appropriate from the dropdown menu.
4. In the second box, enter the canonical event key for the parent event. For some relationships (campaigns and coinciding) you may need to create an umbrella canonical event first. See instructions below.
5. Click “add.”
6. If you would like to view the relationships for a particular canonical event, you can use the search feature at the bottom and then select “view.” This will return the hierarchy using parent-child terminology.

Note: if you can't find the base/inspiration/umbrella event that should already exist for the event you're adjudicating (ex. you are adjudicating a protest at UCLA in solidarity with Yale, but Yale hasn't been adjudicated yet), then record this relationship in the Notes for the canonical record, and then submit a question to the Notion spreadsheet.

⁴ The “Coinciding” relationship category was later changed to “Actions on Special Days/Weeks/Months” in the final data cleaning stage.

Creating Umbrella Events⁵

For campaigns and coinciding events, you will need to create an umbrella event if one does not exist already and a brief event description. For coinciding events, it is likely that the umbrella event already exists (and you should search for one before creating a new one). Typically, you should create an umbrella event and add the child events when it becomes clear that, in that location, the campaign is over. If you suspect that a campaign continues beyond your assigned search parameters, note this in the Notion questions spreadsheet but still create an umbrella event for the appropriate relationships in your search.

To create the umbrella canonical event, following the same instructions as creating a regular canonical event.

Naming Legend for Umbrella Event Keys

Umbrella + School Name/Acronym/Nickname/Event Name (if not campus specific) + Main Issue/Racial Issue + Year + Month(s)

Examples:

Umbrella_Mizzou_Anti-Racism_2015_Oct-Nov

Umbrella_UCBerkeley_XX_XXX

Umbrella_UofT_Labour_2015_XXX

Umbrella_Harvard_Divestment_2015-2016

Umbrella_Mattress_SexualAssault_YEAR_MONTH

Umbrella_MillionStudentMarch_Labour_2015_MONTH

After completing the adjudication for a campaign or coinciding events in your assigned search, double check the umbrella canonical event key, especially the month(s), to ensure it is correct.

If you encounter multiple campaigns or coinciding events in the same location in the same months or any other anomaly, add a question to the sheet in Notion and flag.

Event Description for Umbrella Events (if relevant)

Sometimes the umbrella event key does not contain important identifying information that would be helpful for searching and identifying that campaign or set of coinciding events. In those situations, add to the Umbrella Event Description any helpful terminology or explanation for

⁵ Each protest relationship is a “parent/child” relationship, as outlined above. Umbrella event records do not have any coded data as part of their record in the database, and are created as an intermediary to record the relationships between canonical events. Umbrellas are almost always the “parent” in the relationship, since they serve to aggregate individual canonical events under a specific campaign or coinciding event (though, sometimes they can be the child in a relationship if they are nested underneath an even larger campaign). The only instance where we have used an actual canonical event with coded data to *function* as an umbrella (i.e. the parent in a campaign relationship) is for the strike form, since it is both a campaign and an event under our definitions for both those terms on this project.

identifying that campaign or set of coinciding events; separate each with a return to create a list.
Examples:

- National Day of Action
- Mattress protests (for Carry the Weight)
- Campaign supporting Milo
- Campaign against racist Halloween costumes
- Take Back the Night (a campaign with one umbrella for each academic year)

Canonical Event Keys for Major or Distinctive Umbrella Events

Take Back the Night

Take Back the Night events are part of a larger campaign run by the namesake organization, since they license their event format (decided at the 2022-03-18 team meeting). Therefore, do not create an umbrella event for Take Back the Night protests, but instead link them with a campaign relationship to the appropriate pre-made umbrella based on the academic year (July 1-June 30). *In the interface there is a different umbrella event for each academic year.*

Ex. Umbrella_TakeBackNight_SexualAssault_2015-2016 (for July 1, 2015 to June 30, 2016)

Mizzou

Use these keys when you are entering a solidarity relationship with Mizzou. If the solidarity event only describes the Mizzou events vaguely, the parent event should be

“Umbrella_Mizzou_Anti-Racism_2015_Oct-Nov ”

Grad Student Walkout/Rally	2015-08-26	2015-08-26	20150826_Columbia_Rally/Strike_UniversityGovernance
Anti-Racism Rally/March	2015-10-01	2015-10-01	20151001_Columbia_Rally/March_AntiRacism
Sit-in in Jessie Hall	2015-10-06	2015-10-06	20151006_Columbia_Sit-in_AntiRacism
Homecoming Blockade	2015-10-10	2015-10-10	20151010_Columbia_Blockade_UniversityGovernance
Jonathon Butler's Hunger Strike	2015-11-02	2015-11-09	20151102_Columbia_HungerStrike_UniversityGovernance
Campout	2015-11-02	No End Date	20151102_Columbia_Occupation_UniversityGovernance
Football Player's Boycott/Strike	2015-11-07	2015-11-09	20151107_Columbia_Boycott_UniversityGovernance
Rally/Demonstration (The MARK)	2015-11-07	2015-11-07	20151107_Columbia_Demonstration_CampusClimate
Rally (Melissa Click incident)	2015-11-09	2015-11-09	20151109_Columbia_Rally_CampusClimate
Free Speech Counter-Protest	2015-11-09	2015-11-09	20151109_Columbia_OtherForm_FreeSpeech
Faculty Walkout	2015-11-10	2015-11-10	20151110_Columbia_FacultyWalkout_UniversityGovernance

Pro/Anti-Trump Protests

Create an umbrella event if there is a specific campaign in a location, e.g. a school has an anti-Trump campaign. Do not create umbrella events when there are coinciding pro- and anti-Trump protests

that are happening at the same time, which are especially common on major dates, e.g., Election Day, Inauguration Day.

Removing a Relationship

If you accidentally add a relationship that isn't accurate, you can remove it by searching the child event key in the "View Hierarchy" box of relationships tab. From there, press the delete button beside the appropriate parent event key.

Using Coding Categories to Determine Relationships.

- **What you're seeing across different events**
- **Event descriptions**
- **Campaign (yes/no):** Assume this coding is correct but check Event Description.
- **Related protests involving other universities (text-select):** If selected and campaign (yes/no) is not selected, this event likely is "coinciding," but check Event Description for any clues about explicit coordination.
- **Multiple cities (yes/no):** May be a campaign or coinciding relationship, should check Event Description as well as Campaign (Yes/No) and Related Protests (Text Select).
- **Counterprotest:** Assume this coding is correct but check Event Description.

Step 8: Record Your Progress in the Adjudicator Assignments Spreadsheet

After you have exhausted all the candidate events in your assigned search, be sure to update your progress in the adjudicator assignments spreadsheet within Notion.

1. Enter the *Completion Date*.
2. Ensure that you've recorded all the *Canonical Keys* that you created/edited in the assigned search.
3. Check the *Completed?* box so that the search leaves your queue, and you can begin working on the next.

II. REFEREEING: STEP 5 IN DETAIL

This section contains detailed instructions on the refereeing stage of adjudication. To refresh: refereeing takes place in the expanded event view, and it describes the process of comparing,

evaluating, and selecting the most “correct” coded answer(s) for a given field, to include in the canonical event record.

When building canonical records, you are essentially coding; however, instead of reading an article, you are now pulling all the necessary information from previous codings. Remember: you already have substantial knowledge of the project codebook. Your role as an adjudicator is to ensure that the final dataset of canonical event records contains quality information in line with our codebook standards. **Reference the codebook often, and adjudicate according to its most up-to-date decisions.**

Basics of Refereeing

Now that you have at least one candidate event in the expanded event view, you may now begin adding new information to the canonical event record. As explained above:

First, if you are working with an existing canonical event record, **review that canonical event record fully**, so that you know what information has already been recorded.

Then, check every field for the candidate event(s) for accuracy and completeness. If you are working with a singleton, this will be simpler because you will not need to compare and reconcile the singleton coding with other candidate events. If you are working with multiple candidate events, **go field by field across the candidate events** to referee the content, e.g., read through all the start dates, then all the end dates. As you review this information, **use the add button within each box to move the correct information into the canonical event record.** If multiple candidate events include the exact same information, only rely on one of them to build the canonical event record.

If you find inaccurate, insufficient, or incomplete information in the canonical event record, remove it with the “x” button and replace it with new information from one of your candidate events.

General Principles for Decision-Making

When encountering disagreement between codings - between multiple candidate events that describe the same canonical event or between an existing canonical event record and candidate events describing that same event - you should follow these principles, in this order. Overall, you should **trust the original coding**; in particular, when looking for accuracy within a candidate event record or when comparing candidate event records, assume the original coding is correct, while keeping in mind friendly reminders of known errors in coding listed above.

1. **Codebook rules.** All your decisions should align with the codebook. Consult the codebook whenever needed.
2. **Prioritize “home school” coding.** The reporting from the school where the protest occurs will probably be the most detailed and accurate. Prioritize this coding (or, if that’s not

available, reporting from another school in the same city) when creating or adding to a canonical event record.

3. **Trust the existing Canonical Event Record** unless you are adding information from the home school coding.
4. **Majority.** Trust the information repeated most often within a disagreement.
5. **Return to event/article descriptions.** You might be able to resolve a conflict by returning to the information contained in the event/article descriptions (since these usually contain language taken directly from articles).
6. **Overly inclusive.** Select all that could apply if:) you can't make a decision on a category that has multiple answer options (e.g., Issue), 2) you can't make a decision on which text select corresponds with a preset.

Using the Meta-Data

There is a meta-data field at the top of each candidate event coding and each canonical event record containing identifying information, such as the article title or publication name. The meta-data will be relevant for refereeing only on rare occasions:

- Comparing publication dates while refereeing multiple codings of the same event, i.e. if one coding was from an article published the day of a protest event before it ended, and another coding from an article published the day after the protest ended.
- Confirming the "place of protest," i.e. the more specific place where the protest happened (at the publishing university, at another university, or entirely off campus). Note: by default, we assume that a protest occurred completely on the campus of the publishing university unless otherwise indicated in another field.

Article Descriptions

You should read article descriptions, but you do not need to add them to the canonical record. They are particularly helpful when making sense of complex events, or identifying relationships among canonical events.

Event Descriptions

When refereeing event descriptions from multiple codings of the same article, select the event description that contains the most detail on the essential event description elements:

- Actors
- Form
- Where
- Issue
- Target
- Solidarity

- Demands
- Timing

The process of adding canonical event descriptions to the canonical event record is unique. If you identify a candidate event description that will be the canonical event description, you should press the “Copy” button within the appropriate candidate event box (or copy the portion of the text that you want using your computer’s “copy” shortcut), then press the pencil “edit” button in the canonical event description field, and then past your text into the pop-up window.

Do not include any “fixed” information, e.g. DATA-CLEANING FIX: []

Editing, Combining, and Fixing Event Descriptions

If you need to combine two or more candidate event descriptions together to contain all of the essential information, or if you need to add more information to the existing canonical event description, simply copy and paste the relevant text from the candidate event (or write it yourself) directly into the freeform canonical event description box. Try to use whole sentences.

If an event description is very short and/or missing important details, you should still trust the coding—unless you see indications that the event should not have been coded at all; in that case, reject the candidate event. If you see from the Event Description(s) that more events need to be coded (e.g. the candidate event is really multiple protest events and should have been coded as such) see [instructions below](#) on returning to the Pass 1 interface.

Ensure that the event description has the university name of where the protest event occurs. Watch out for any descriptions that only record the building name, as this may indicate that the location information is incorrect.

Refereeing the Essential+ Fields

The fields that will be most important for our final analysis are:

- Start-Date and End-Date
- Location
- Presets for
 - Form
 - Issue
 - Racial Issue
 - Target
- Movement Organizations (text select)

If you see errors or missing information in any of these fields, you should create an adjudicator-created variable ([detailed below](#)).

Location Standardization

The standard format for location is: City, Two Letter State/Province Code, USA/Canada. Examples:

- Waterloo, ON, Canada
- Los Angeles, CA, USA

Select the location location that matches this format exactly. If none of the candidate events have the correctly formatted location, add an [adjudicator created variable](#).

We should always verify the location information recorded in the candidate event, especially in comparison to the event description. This can be as simple as just searching up building names or parks to make sure they are consistent with everything else mentioned. Add the location to the event description if it's not entirely clear, e.g. only a building name is noted. Also look out for situations in which a university has buildings in different cities (especially for Boston-area schools; e.g., Tufts has buildings in Medford and Boston; Harvard does in Cambridge and Boston).

Working with Text Selects: Matching with Presets and Other Considerations

Background

The text selects serve different purposes in this project. During coding in the Pass 1 interface, the text select captures information we have not yet standardized (e.g., police actions, protest size) and, for the Essential+ presets, they provide corroborating information. When we analyze the final data set, we will use the text selects to do topic modeling of broader categories (e.g., look for faculty hiring as a theme within Racial Issues: University Governance). We may use the text selects for easy access to specific examples that we can write about, to illustrate quantitative trends. We also may use the text selects to identify specific case studies to focus on in greater detail.

General Guidelines for Choosing Text Selects

While refereeing, you should choose the most relevant text selects that add specific information. However, we do not want you to spend a lot of time deliberating between text selects. Some general guidelines:

- When in doubt, choose more text selects. Don't overthink it.
- Do not choose text selects that provide extraneous, irrelevant information (e.g., "Jesus" and "Nazis" should not be selected as the issue text select for an anti-abortion protest because they are not central to protest).
- Do not include quotes if possible.
- If the event description is short and incomplete, check the article description.

- If the text is extremely long, which is more common with the earliest codings, select the longer chunks of text; do not return to Pass 1/MPEDS to correct this.
- For protests coded more than once:
 - If text selects from different coders contain the same content but one is slightly longer (e.g., “civilian oversight” vs “civilian oversight of police”), choose the longer one.
 - If the majority of candidate event codings chose the same text selects but there is one outlier text select (with no corresponding preset or other confirming information) and you cannot determine if it is correct without going back to the Pass 1 interface, go with the majority and do not choose the outlier.
 - If there are two different text selects and no majority and no way to determine which is correct without going back to Pass 1/MPEDS, select them both to avoid losing possibly useful data.

Text Select for the Essential+ Presets (Form, Issue, Racial Issue, Target)

You will need to choose both coded presets and the most relevant text selects. Generally, you should strive for something between quickly selecting everything and slowly corroborating every preset and every text select. More specifically, for each of these fields, you should read over all the presets and all the text selects with the Event Description in mind, to get a sense of the overall picture. Choose all the text selects that could be relevant to the presets you are adding to the canonical event record. Look for “good enough” and “likely” text selects, rather than focusing on choosing The Very Best One.

- For each of those preset categories, try to identify at least one text select (or more).
- When there are multiple candidate events - go with what the majority of coders selected. If there are outliers (e.g., a preset or text selected by only one of a few coders):
 - Look more closely for corroborating information in the text select.
 - Keep in mind the changes to the codebook, particularly for Issues and Racial Issues, e.g. the definition for hate speech got narrower later in the coding.
- If both the preset and the text select are missing for form or issue, assume that this information was not provided in the original article.
- Over time, you will likely develop “shorthands” for identifying text selects. For example:
 - If the Target is University/school, the text select should be the university’s name.
 - Look for common words that come up with a preset, e.g “racism” and “racial discrimination” for Racial Issue: Anti-Racism; “safe space” for Racial Issue: Campus Climate; a (White man’s) name or a flag for Racial Issues: Racist/Racialized Symbols.

If Text Select is Missing for Essential+ Presets, Movement Organizations, or Other University Where Protest Occurs

For Form, Issue, and Racial Issue: If there is no text select to corroborate a preset but the preset is plausible (esp from the Event Description or other content), that's OK.

For Target, Movement Organizations, or Other University Where Protest Occurs: If the text select is missing but you have reason to believe that information is in the original article (e.g., based on content in the Event Description or text selected with an Actor's name), return to the Pass 1 interface to select that text.

Text Select for Categories Other than Essential+

- **University Responses and Police Actions-** Ignore these text selects for regular coder accounts.
- **Part of Protest Occurs Off Campus -** If any text has been selected for this category, just select one chunk of text. In our final data set, this will be recorded as a simple "yes/no" answer. The rationale is that we have decided we are not going to analyze the micro-geography of protests, e.g. which streets protestors walked on, because this information is not consistently reported and is not central to our research questions.
- **Size-** If multiple sizes are text selected: Select the smallest number of protestors and the largest number of protestors (if it is vague whether the numbers refer to individual protestors, you usually can assume that they do. Don't select numbers of subgroups (e.g. professors, organizers, organizations, bystanders/observers) or organizations. When in doubt, select the largest number.

Adjudicating Police Actions

The police actions text selects and presets have been coded in separate PA accounts, as PA codings. For your assigned searches, candidate search results may contain PA codings, which are identifiable because the coder ID will start with "PA_", e.g. PA_Moneet. The PA codings contain more limited information than a regular coding of a protest event: location, date, form, police action text selects, and 4 preset questions on police actions (Preset II in MPEDS) as well as event_desc (which only contains the "Original Event ID" [OEID] of the candidate event that the PA coding is based off of). Each PA coding has its own Event ID now, too.

Occasionally there will be multiple PA codings for the same canonical event. These may be police actions reported in different news articles or, infrequently, multiple PA codings of the same event reported in the same article.

Adding Police Actions for Already-Adjudicated Canonical Events⁶

As of 2022-03-23: For assigned searches you have already adjudicated, you will need to pull up the PA codings for those assignments (locations within a time frame- in Notion in your Complete tab) and add the PA information to the appropriate canonical event record. Consult [this PA list](#), organized into 2015-16 and 2016-17, to identify the locations/time frames that have PA codings that need to be incorporated into canonical events.

Using the Pass 2 interface:

1. In the Candidate Events search tab, under filter, set the location and start date parameters from your Notion assignment and then add coder_ID filter to: contains "PA."
 - a. Currently the "starts with" term is bringing up an error, but Alex is working on that; in the meantime, set Sort to coder_ID descending so that amritpal's coding is at the bottom of the search results—do not adjudicate amritpal's events here (since they are not PA codings).
2. In the search results, identify the PA codings that describe the same canonical event (based on location, date, form, etc), and add those to the grid.
3. Match the PA event(s) to the appropriate canonical event key. Search the canonical event records for that PA coding's date and location (e.g. 20151001_Austin) and add that canonical event to the grid.
4. See adjudication instructions below.
5. Check as completed. It will already be linked to the canonical event..
6. In the PA list, initial the PA coding(s) you have completed.

Adjudicating Police Actions while Adjudicating Candidate Events

Once you have matched any PA codings to the appropriate canonical event record, you only should adjudicate the Police Actions text selects and the four Police Actions presets. Add these fields to the canonical event record you are working on and adjudicate them as normal, including marking the PA coding as complete when you are finished. Ignore everything else in the PA coding; the other information exists only for search and matching purposes. Note that the OEID in the event_desc might be useful for matching the PA coding to the appropriate candidate event and/or canonical event.

If you need to do mini-adjudication between multiple PA codings of the same canonical event, the principle is: add more substance. In other words, add all the text selects and all the codes under the four Police Actions questions.

⁶ In winter 2023, adjudication was already in progress while university responses and police actions were still being coded by a separate team of RAs.

- For example, if one PA coding has N/A for Type of Police and the other has Univ Police, select Univ Police. Or if one PA coding has Univ Police and Govt Police and the other only has Univ Police, select both Univ Police and Govt Police.
- However, do not duplicate text selects.
- If there are two text selects with similar text but one is longer than the other, use the longer one.

Some 2015-16 canonical event records contain Police Actions text select but no presets. This is because those text selects were erroneously added while adjudicating regular candidate events. You can keep the existing text select if it is the same as the text select for the PA coding. However, the PA coding will have the most up-to-date and relevant text.

Friendly Reminders: Known Errors in Prior Coding that Can Be Easily Corrected

You are more likely to encounter these errors in the earlier coding, which tend to be the earlier publication dates.

- **Start Date:** Future protests, i.e., events with a start date after the publication date, should be rejected.
- **Preset: Racial Issue: Anti-racism:** should only be selected if the text select makes reference to the words racism, racist, racial injustice, bigotry, and/or discrimination, or to mistreatment experienced by named racial/ethnic groups. This category was coded broadly earlier on and then we formulated the more specific, correct definition here.
- **Preset: Target** for solidarity events should be No Target if no local target is mentioned in the corresponding text-select (or else left blank).

Refereeing Complications

Refereeing becomes more complex and more time consuming when there are contradictions between candidate events, when there are contradictions between the information in the existing canonical event record and new candidate event(s) you are reviewing, and/or when important information is missing. The instructions below are intended to guide your process by maximizing both accuracy and efficiency.

When to Reference the Original Article

You should always **avoid referring to the original article** because that is time-consuming. However, if there are contradictions between codings that you cannot resolve using the adjudication interface (e.g. the event descriptions) or if there is only one coding of a candidate event with

contradictory coding within it (e.g., event description implies multiple cities but that box was not checked), you can briefly reference the original article. Do this by pressing the article number hyperlink within the candidate event metadata box at the top of the page. The sections below provide more specific guidelines for when this is merited.

Merging Protests

While rare, sometimes two separate protest events merge into one event (ex. two separately organized marches meet and begin to rally together). Ensure that this dynamic is noted in the event description for both events, but you do NOT need to create any additional canonical events. Duplicate any information that relates to the “merged” protest in both existing canonical event records. Do NOT add any relationships.

Add to the Notes field for both merging events: “This event merged with [canonical key].”

Riots (vs. Disruptive Protests)

We want to move away from coding any events as riots (we probably have very few, anyway). Add a question in Notion if it’s not clear what the event should be coded as. Add to the “Notes” in the canonical record: “This was originally coded as a riot” if any candidate events used to build the record were coded as a riot. If there was any property damage, ensure that it’s recorded as a form.

III. ADDING INFORMATION USING ADJUDICATOR-CREATED VARIABLES

An adjudicator-created variable is a variable that you can add during the adjudication process. Creating an adjudicator-created variable should be avoided but may be necessary. The interface only allows adjudicator-created variables for the following “Essential+” fields:

- Start Date or End Date
- Location
- Presets for:
 - Form
 - Issue
 - Racial Issue
 - Target

How to Create an Adjudicator-Created Variable

Simply press the “plus” button for the desired field. A lightbox window will pop-up allowing you to add the necessary information, which will then show up as a green box within the canonical event record you are working on.

When to Create an Adjudicator-Created Variable

1. If you identify inconsistencies/errors in the Essential+ fields. Most likely, important information is included in another field—usually the Article Description, Event Description, and Text Select—but not in the Essential+ field or a codebook rule was not followed (e.g. location is not “Virtual” for a virtual protest).
 - a. Reminder: adjudicator-created variables are needed to standardize the location if it does not exactly match the [standardized location format](#).
2. The following are all changes made to the codebook mid-way through coding:
 - Form: Soapbox preachers - code as Rally/Demonstration (not Other Form)
 - Issues:
 - LGB+ or Transgender Issues: code as For or Against
 - Hate Speech or Hate Crime: may need to be added for anti-LGBTQ+ or anti-Trans protest
 - Islamophobia or anti-Semitism: code as Faith-based discrimination + Issue: Far Right/Alt Right (For) + (if relevant) Racial Issue.
 - Police Violence/Anti-Law Enforcement: code if it is an anti-police protest with no racial issue.

To identify the correct information, you may need to consult the original article, though you should avoid that.

IV. RETURNING TO THE PASS 1 MPEDS INTERFACE TO CODE

You should only return to the Pass 1 MPEDS interface for these reasons:

- a. To correct or add important information missing from an existing candidate event record
- b. To create a new candidate event
- c. To verify and, if needed, correct foundational errors that are evident in Pass 1 but cannot be corrected in Pass 1 (ex. to confirm that the event should have been coded in the first place, if that's unclear)

A. To Correct or Add Important Information Missing from an Existing Candidate Event Record or Correct Existing Information Related to Where the Protest Occurred

Some of specific reasons to correct previous coding:

- For Yes/No and Preset fields that don't have an adjudicator created variable
- A protest event occurred in multiple cities but "Yes/No: Multiple Cities" was not selected
- "Text Select: Other University Where Protest Occurs" is inaccurate or blank, but you know from the event description that the protest event took place at a campus other than the publishing university.

Instructions for Correcting an Existing Coding

1. Go to the Pass 1 MPEDS interface and log in as the original coder (using logins from [this sheet](#)).
2. Code the correct start-date and location (so the system doesn't discard the record).
3. Code the appropriate information.
4. Make note of the Event ID.
5. Return to the Pass 2 adjudication interface, and run a new candidate event search specifically for the Event ID you just noted.
6. Add the event to your expanded event view, and then add the new information to the canonical event record.
7. Notify the project manager if the coding is no longer within your assigned search date-range/location and/or if you added any text select for police actions and/or university responses. This is important because we need to ensure that someone adjudicates the events and/or codes that new text select.

B. To Create a New Candidate Event

You should code new protest events (i.e. new candidate events) in the following situations:

- **The article description and/or event description refers to another codeable protest** on the same date and in the same location but the event coding does not come up in your candidate events search results.
- **A complex event was erroneously miscoded as single event**
In earlier periods of the project in particular, RAs may have grouped separate events into a single coding entry, especially if these events were part of a larger complex event. This error often will be evident from the Event Description and/or in the candidate events search results (assuming the protests were part of a complex event that occurred in the same

location and on or around the same start date). Before making any corrections in the Pass 1 MPEDS interface, review the candidate event search results and search the Canonical Event Records to check if there are multiple codings of that article or codings of other articles with the same canonical event; someone else may have coded it correctly. If so, you can use those candidate event codings to build the canonical event. If not, review the event description carefully for any clarifying information (e.g., maybe the original article did not include location or start date for some parts of the complex event).

Instructions for Coding New Events

1. Log into Pass 1 using your regular coder ID
2. Enter the Article ID for the original article that you suspect has a missing event, review to ensure that there is a codeable event, and if there is, code it. (If there is not, you can stop here.)
3. Make note of the Event ID.
4. Search for the event using the Event Selection pane.
5. Return to the Pass 2 adjudication interface, and run a new candidate event search specifically for the Event ID you just noted.
6. Add the event to your expanded event view, and then create a new canonical event record or add the new information to an existing canonical event record
7. Notify the project manager if any newly created events are no longer within your assigned search date-range/location and/or if the new event has any text select for police actions and/or university responses. This is important because we need to ensure that someone adjudicates the events and/or codes that new text select.

V. AD HOC ADJUDICATION

This section contains instructions for adjudication that was done outside the typical assignment processes (which is all events at a specific location for a specific year).

Montreal 2012 and Montreal 2015

Articles related to the student strikes in 2012, and again in 2015, raised new methodological and coding questions. As such, adjudication for these events differs from the typical processes.

Because of the complicated federated structure of student unions in Quebec, which function similar to labour unions, and which allowed different faculty/department unions within a single university to differ in the start and end date of their strikes, the length of their strikes, and other protest forms included in their strike actions (picketing, blockade, etc), canonical keys for the Quebec student strikes should follow a unique naming convention.

If the candidate events are describing strikes by a specific student association at a specific school, include the school and the faculty/department/association abbreviation in the canonical event key. If no abbreviation is known, use a shortened version of the name of the faculty/department. For example:

- 20120214_Montreal-UQAM-FineArts_Strike_Tuition
- 20120315_Montreal-Concordia-CSU_Strike_Tuition
- 20120320_Montreal-McGill-PGSS_Strike_Tuition

If the candidate events are describing the general province-wide strike, they should be added to the following canonical event key already created:

- 20120213_Quebec_Strike_Tuition

If the candidate events are describing a general strike at a university or college, without additional detail explaining which associations or faculties were on strike, include the name of the institution in the canonical event key, with an approximate start date on the first day of the first strike at that institution or the first day of the month in which students at that institution started striking. If this start date information is unknown, use 20130213, which was the first day of the province-wide strike. For example:

- 20120214_Montreal-UdeM_Strike_Tuition
- 20120302_Montreal-Concordia_Strike_Tuition
- 20120319_Montreal-McGill_Strike_Tuition

Known start dates can be found in the “Quebec 2012 Student Strikes” spreadsheet, [here](#).

VI. QUALITY CONTROL/FEEDBACK

Data managers will use your individual adjudication assignments spreadsheet to do spot checks on your adjudication work, e.g., to check how you constructed a canonical event and to ensure no candidate events are missed.

For questions/conflicts/issues that arise, use the new tab in the Coder Questions spreadsheet to submit an issue for follow-up. Anticipated situations where you should request follow-up:

- You are unsure which candidate event has the accurate information (i.e. coding conflict)
 - Between multiple codings of the same article (most resolved by checking the article)
 - Between codings of different articles with discrepant information about the same event
- Unsure of which canonical event record to contribute to (conflicts between them)
- When to fix existing coding

- Identifying and adding Relationships (*more to come*)

Feedback Partners

Every adjudicator has a feedback partner:

- Sara; Tianna
- Kristen; David
- Tsitsi; Moneet

On Fridays, the “Nominator” from each pair will nominate a recently completed adjudication search they found difficult, or that they think should be reviewed twice (ideally this search will have around 10 candidate events but probably no more than 15; avoid singletons). The “Second Adjudicator” from that pair will then use the **CLIFF training server** to adjudicate the search by the Thursday evening before the next team meeting. A data manager will then compile the canonical event records from both adjudicators into a comparable spreadsheet.

At the beginning of team meetings, feedback partners will review their adjudication feedback sheet together and make decisions on any disagreement. During the second half of the meeting, we will address any outstanding discrepancies and questions. **The Nominators will be responsible for updating their canonical records, if needed, based on any decisions made in the meeting,** because their records are in the production SHERIFF server.

Then on that same Friday, whomever was just Second Adjudicator will switch to Nominator to nominate a search and the roles are reversed for the week. Therefore, you will be adjudicating a “feedback search” in the CLIFF training server every second week.

APPENDICES

Glossary

- **Assigned Search:** The start-date range/location that you will be assigned by a project manager to search for candidate events for adjudication.
- **Candidate Event Actions:** The set of 5 action buttons at the top of each candidate event: Add all values; Link to canonical event; Flag for later; Mark completed; Remove from grid (see figure X).
- **Candidate Event Coding:** Each individual coding of a protest event.
- **Canonical Event Key:** The name of each canonical event record, which follows a strict naming convention to make canonical events easier to search during the adjudication process. Format is: StartDate_Location(City)_Form_Issue
- **Canonical Event Record:** The new, unique record we are now creating (and updating) for each unique protest event. It will be comprised of elements from one or more candidate events.
- **Event Mention:** Some articles reference a canonical event but do not provide any additional information for the canonical event record. We only use these articles for the purposes of recording an “event mention,” which is a measure of media attention.
- **Event Selection Pane:** The portion of the interface where you can select relevant candidate events to adjudicate.
- **Expanded Event View Pane:** The portion of the interface where you can visually compare up to four candidate events, view the selected canonical event record, and add relevant coding elements from the candidate events to the canonical event record.
- **Meta-Data:** the header row of the expanded event view that contains the article title, publication name, publication date, article ID, and coder name.
- **Multiple/Double-Coded Article:** When more than one RA coded the same article so there are multiple candidate event codings that are very similar.
- **Multi-Article Event:** When the same event has been reported on and coded in different articles, so there are multiple codings of the same event that need to be compared, reconciled and/or combined into the canonical event record.
- **Outliers:** Random codings (eg. approximate start-date or errors in location/start-date) that are difficult to identify and may need additional review to determine which canonical event record they belong to.
- **Pass 1:** Article-level coding in the MPEDS interface.
- **Pass 2:** Event-level adjudication and canonical record creation in the new adjudication interface.
- **Pass 3:** Canonical event record adjudication, details TBD.
- **Place of Protest:** Whether the protest occurs a) at the publishing university, completely on campus, b) at the publishing university, both on/off campus c) at a university other than the publishing university, or d) completely off-campus. Not to be confused with Location, which we define as a municipality.

- **Refereeing:** The process of reviewing, reconciling, and selecting fields for the canonical event record by comparing articles side-by-side within the expanded event view.
- **Singleton:** A candidate event coding that is the only coding used to construct a canonical event record. The most simple and most likely adjudication scenario.
- **Umbrella Event:** an adjudicator-created canonical event that does not contain any coded information, and only used to describe hierarchical relationships among canonical protest events.

Interface Screenshots

Search Tab

Event Selection

Search [Candidate Events](#) [Canonical Events](#) [Relationships](#)

Search

Example: Mizzou OR Missouri, Quebec AND students

Filter

start_date	▼	is greater than or equ	▼	2016-05-01	✕
start_date	▼	is less than	▼	2016-07-01	✕
---	▼	---	▼	Value...	✕

Sort

start_date	▼	ascending	▼	✕
---	▼	---	▼	✕
---	▼	---	▼	✕

[Search](#)

Candidate Event Search Results Tab

Event Selection

Search
Candidate Events
Canonical Events
Relationships

Search (20 results)

Recent

<p>start_date: 2016-05-01 location: Chicago, Illinois, USA title: Anti-Trump protesters take to downtown streets, say 'not my president' desc: Protesters disrupted alt-right blogger Milo Yiannopoulos' presentation at DePaul University. Demonstrators were protesting Yiannopoulos racist rhetoric.</p>	<p>event_id: 24755 article_id: 13865 coder: TsitsiM</p>	<p>No flags Add to grid </p>
<p>start_date: 2016-05-01 location: Chicago, Illinois, USA title: Free speech panel debate First Amendment desc: Conservative provocateur Milo Yiannopoulos visited DePaul University in May. Students protested the event citing Yiannopoulos racist rhetoric.</p>	<p>event_id: 24754 article_id: 13626 coder: TsitsiM</p>	<p>No flags Add to grid </p>
<p>start_date: 2016-05-15 location: Virtual title: Petitions fly and protests promised with Milo Yiannopolous visit desc: The event in this article is an online Change.org petition, requesting DePaul university to cancel Milo Yiannopoulos' impending visit. The petition reads that he encourages oppression via his xenophobic statements and ideologies. The petition currently has 376 out of 500 signatures requested. DATA CLEANING FIX: - Added "General Issues - Far Right/Alt Right (Against)" ADDITIONAL FIXES - Fixed netition location to virtual - Captured 'Text Select - action/form'</p>	<p>event_id: 6029 article_id: 6606 coder: SalinaFixed</p>	<p>No flags Add to grid </p>
<p>start_date: 2016-05-22 location: Chicago, IL, USA title: Students stage sit-in, vent over campus tensions</p>	<p>event_id: 31555 article_id: 6642 coder: SaraFixed</p>	<p>No flags Add to grid </p>

Canonical Event Selection Tab

« Hide Pane

Event Selection

Search Candidate Events Canonical Events Relationships

Search

Key...

key: Milo_Chicago_2016 **Status:** In progress
start_date: **Last edited:**
location: Chicago, IL, USA **Current active event**
notes: This is the main event for the protest against Milo in Chicago in 2016. This is filler text to try to break this part of it. This is filler text to try to break this part of it. This is filler text to try to break this part of it. This is filler text to try to break this part of it.
desc: The event was a protest outside of Yiannopoulos' event at the DePaul student center, which eventually moved to the quad. It was intended to create an outlet for students to express their opinions on the event and was attended by 100-150 people. DATA CLEANING FIX: - Added "General Issues - Far

Candidate Event Actions (within Expanded Event View)

metadata **Event 6031**

Actions:

Left to Right:

Add all values; Link to canonical event; Flag for later; Mark completed; Remove from grid

Relationships Tab⁷

« Hide Pane

Event Selection

Search Candidate Events Canonical Events Relationships

Add relationship

Key 1... Key 2... Campaign ▾ Add +

View hierarchy

Key...

```
graph TD; L1[action 1] --> L2[action 2]; L2 --> L3[action 3]; L3 --> L4[action 4]; L4 --> L5a[action 5]; L4 --> L5b[action 6]; L5a --> L6a[action 7]; L5b --> L6b[action 8]; L6b --> L7a[action 9]; L6b --> L7b[action 10];
```

level 1 action 1

level 2 action 2

level 3 action 3

level 4 action 4

level 5 action 5 action 6

level 6 action 7 action 8

level 7 action 9 action 10

sequence 1 sequence 2 sequence 3

⁷ This was the original screenshot from the guidelines, before the relationships tab was fully developed.

Relationships Tab (as used)⁸

Search	Candidate Events	Canonical Events	Relationships	
Add relationship				
<input type="text" value="Key 1... (Child Event)"/>				
<input type="text" value="is part of this campaign"/>				▼
<input type="text" value="Key 2... (Parent Event)"/>				Add
<hr/>				
View hierarchy				
<input type="text" value="Key..."/>				View
<hr/>				

⁸ The relationships tab as it was used by adjudicators. This screenshot was not included in the original version of the *Adjudication Guidelines*.